

Phosphoryl Bromide as a Polar Solvent

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Compounds of phosphoryl bromide with the Lewis acids, sulphur trioxide, tin (rv) bromide, tin (rv) chloride, titanium (rv) chloride, antimony (v) chloride, aluminium chloride, and aluminium bromide, have been isolated and a compound with antimony(III) bromide has been indicated by a study of the conductance of the system. Density, viscosity, specific conductance, and freezing points of some of the solutions have been studied. Phosphoryl bromide also forms compounds with lithium bromide and nitrogen bases. Wherever possible, a study of the specific conductance of these systems has been made to ascertain the nature of these compounds. The formation of these compounds and their properties have been explained on the basis of ionisation of the solvent as: $\text{POBr}_3 \rightleftharpoons \text{POBr}_2^+ + \text{Br}^-$.

Conductometric titrations between the solutions of tin(rv) bromide and lithium bromide or nitrogen bases further support the autoionisation of phosphoryl bromide, as shown above. A close examination of the composition of the various solvates formed also indicates a further possibility of the existence of the ions $(\text{POBr})^{2+}$, $(\text{PO})_2^{2+}$, $(\text{P}_2\text{O}_2\text{Br}_2)^+$ in solutions of molten phosphoryl bromide in addition to the existence of ions $(\text{POBr}_2)^+$ $(\text{Br}^-)^-$, and $(\text{POBr}_4)^-$.

Although phosphoryl bromide has been long known¹, its structure and chemistry have only been recently investigated²⁻³. Its compounds with titanium(rv) bromide and iron(III) bromide have been reported by Sheldon and Tyree⁴. Greenwood and Worrall⁵ in studying the nature of its complex with gallium(III) bromide have indicated the possibility of the existence of dibromo-oxophosphonium $(\text{POBr}_2)^+$ ions in the complex. If the above indication of the existence of $(\text{POBr}_2)^+$ ions is correct, the pure liquid phosphoryl bromide is likely to exist in the equilibrium:

It is also possible that the bromide ions may be further solvated in phosphoryl bromide to produce tetrabromo-oxophosphate $(\text{POBr}_4)^-$ ions. The aim of the present work is to study the nature of the solutions of the Lewis acids, nitrogen bases, and alkali bromides in phosphoryl bromide in order to throw some light on the existence of the equilibrium as indicated by equation (i).

Sulphur trioxide is miscible with phosphoryl bromide in all proportions to provide viscous solutions. A plot of specific conductance vs. composition of the mixture, as repre-

1. Berger, *Compt. rend.*, 1908, 146, 400; *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1908, iv, 3, 721.

2. Charnley and Skinner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 450.

3. Siebert, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1954, 275, 210.

4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 4775.

5. *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, 6, 34.

sented by molar ratio of (sulphur trioxide/phosphoryl bromide) is presented in Fig. 1. It is evident that with the addition of sulphur trioxide to phosphoryl bromide, conductance of the solution increases. The plot shows two sharp breaks, indicating the formation of the compounds of compositions $\text{POBr}_3 \cdot \text{SO}_3$ and $\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 2\text{SO}_3$. The specific conductance corresponding to the two compounds is $0.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $8.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, which is much higher than that of the two individual components, phosphoryl bromide ($>4 \times 10^{-8} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)⁵ and sulphur trioxide⁶ ($>1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

FIG. 1. Specific conductance of SO_3 & Sb(m) bromide in phosphoryl bromide at 60° .

FIG. 2

The compound 2-sulphur trioxide-phosphoryl bromide ($2\text{SO}_3 \cdot \text{POBr}_3$) is quite stable and can be easily purified by distilling at 86° under normal pressure. Variation of the specific conductance with temperature has been studied in the temperature range of 25° to 60° and a plot between the logarithm of molar conductance ($\log \mu$) and the reciprocal of absolute temperature ($1/T \times 10^4 \text{ K}^{-1}$) has been found to be a straight line over the entire range (Fig. 2). The energy of activation of ionic migration (E_μ) has been calculated to be 6.708 kcal./mole.

Complex formation is accompanied by a considerable increase in the viscosity of the system. The viscosity of the pure complex $2\text{SO}_3 \cdot \text{POBr}_3$ at 60° is about six times the viscosity of pure phosphoryl bromide⁵ and about twenty times the viscosity of pure sulphur trioxide⁷ at 30° . Density and viscosity of the compound have also been determined for the temperature range of 25° to 60° and the plot of logarithm of viscosity ($\log \eta$) against ($1/T \times 10^4 \text{ K}^{-1}$) is a straight line (Fig. 3). The energy of activation of viscous flow has been found out to be 4.9 kcal./mole. Since the energy of activation of ionic migration differs very much from the energy of activation of viscous flow, the degree of dissociation cannot be identified

6. Narula, S. P., Ph. D. Thesis, Panjab University, 1962.

7. Hynes and Tiley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2348.

with the reduced conductance and further indicates that the compound is not a univalent electrolyte.

FIG. 3. Variation of logarithm of viscosity with reciprocal of absolute temperature.

FIG. 4. Specific conductance of tin (IV) chloride & bromide in phosphoryl bromide.

Since the two compounds ($\text{SO}_3 \cdot \text{POBr}_3$) and ($2\text{SO}_3 \cdot \text{POBr}_3$) are much more conducting than the two components, evidently these are more ionic in nature. Sulphur trioxide is known to have a tendency to acquire a higher co-ordination and the sulphate ion (SO_4)²⁻ is, of course, the most stable of these structures. Hexa-co-ordination of sulphur, though not very common, is indicated in the compounds SF_6 and $(\text{OH})_3\text{S}(\text{CN})_3$ ⁹ and has also been shown to exist in the solutions of sulphur trioxide in various oxo-bases by Paul *et al.*⁹ On the basis of the ionisation of phosphoryl bromide, as indicated in equation (4), and the conductance of the compound, the nature of sulphur trioxide-phosphoryl bromide ($\text{SO}_3 \cdot \text{POBr}_3$) compound may be represented as

(SO_3Br)⁻ is quite conceivable with the tetra-co-ordination of sulphur atom, though it has not been reported in the literature so far. The ion (SO_3Cl)⁻, however, has already been postulated¹⁰. The compound $\text{SO}_3 \cdot \text{POBr}_3$ may be largely undissociated in view of its moderate conductance. It is far more difficult to indicate precisely the nature of the compound $2\text{SO}_3 \cdot \text{POBr}_3$ as it is unusual for donor molecules to form complexes with two acceptor molecules. Compounds of this type with aluminium halides, are however, known¹¹⁻¹². On the basis of the existence of (POBr_3)⁺, this compound may be represented as

9. Jander and Scholz, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1943, 192, 1933.

9. *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 247.

10. Smith, *Chem. Rev.*, 1938, 23, 165.

11. Brown *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 78, 2020.

12. Long and Bailey, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, 59, 594.

Since the physical measurements on viscosity and conductance, just outlined, do not support formation of a uni-univalent electrolyte, it may be represented as a uni-divalent compound as

The monobromo-oxophosphonium ion $(\text{POBr})^{2+}$ has so far not been indicated in the literature, but its existence is quite probable, as will be seen in the case of a few other systems which follow.

Tin(IV) bromide and phosphoryl bromide are freely miscible with each other in the molten state and though both have a very poor specific conductance individually, yet their solutions have been found to be much more conducting. The plot of sp. conductance against molar ratio of (Sn^{IV} bromide/phosphoryl bromide) at 60° is shown in Fig. 4. There are two breaks in the curve corresponding to the compositions $\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$ (compound isolated) and $\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot \text{POBr}_3$. The specific conductance corresponding to these two compositions is $4.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $3.95 \times 10^{-3} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. Since it has been possible to isolate the disolvate tin(IV) bromide-2-phosphoryl bromide ($\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$), and to purify it by distillation under reduced pressure, further physical measurements have been carried out to study its nature. Variation of sp. conductance of this compound between 25° and 60° has been studied and a graph between $\log \mu$ (μ =molar conductance) and $1/T \times 10^4$ (K°) has been plotted (Fig. 2). The plot is a straight line and corresponds to the energy of activation of ionic migration (E_μ) of 1.72 kcal./mole. Measurements of density and viscosity of this compound at each 5° interval between 25° and 60° have been carried out. A plot (Fig. 3) of the logarithm of viscosity ($\log \eta$) vs. $1/T \times 10^4$ (K°) is slightly curved over the range and corresponds to an energy of activation of viscous flow (E_η) of 3.67 kcal./mole. The degree of dissociation cannot be identified with the reduced conductance here also as in the case of $2\text{SO}_3 \cdot \text{POBr}_3$. Therefore, the compound may not act as a uni-univalent electrolyte.

Tin(IV) chloride dissolves in molten phosphoryl bromide at 90° in all proportions in an exothermic reaction. To find out the composition of the compounds formed, if any, freezing points of mixtures of various compositions have been determined and are plotted against the mole percentage composition in Fig. 5. The maximum at 33 mole% tin(IV) chloride corresponds to the composition $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$. It has been possible to isolate the pure white crystalline compound tin(IV) chloride-2-phosphoryl bromide ($\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$) (m.p. 90°) in carbon tetrachloride medium. To study the nature of this compound and to check the existence of any other compound between these two components, sp. conductance of mixtures of various compositions has been studied at 100°. Fig. 4 represents variations of sp. conductance with molar ratio of tin(IV) chloride/phosphoryl bromide. The graph shows a sharp break at 0.5 molar ratio [tin(IV) chloride/phosphoryl bromide] which represents the formation of the compound, tin(IV) chloride-2-phosphoryl bromide ($\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$). There is another slight discontinuity at molar ratio of 1:1 representing the compound tin(IV) chloride] phosphoryl bromide ($\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot \text{POBr}_3$). Tin(IV) chloride and phosphoryl bromide have low sp. conductance [tin(IV) chloride = $6 \times 10^{-11} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and phosphoryl bromide = $4 \times 10^{-8} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$], but the sp. conductance corresponding to the composition $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$ is $6.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is much higher than

that of its components and indicates the formation of a compound which is more ionic in nature.

Titanium(IV) chloride similarly forms a disolvate titanium (IV) chloride-2-phosphoryl bromide ($\text{TiCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$) with phosphoryl bromide, which is monomolecular.

Tin and titanium are well known for their tendency to acquire hexa-co-ordination¹⁴⁻¹⁵. On this basis and the probable ionisation of the solvent, as indicated by equation (5), the disolvates of tin(IV) bromide, tin(IV) chloride, and titanium(IV) chloride could be represented as having the following nature:

This accounts for the higher conductance of the compounds as compared to that of the components. It is rather more difficult to say much about the nature of the monosolvates formed by tin(IV) bromide and tin(IV) chloride with phosphoryl bromide ($\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot \text{POBr}_3$ and $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot \text{POBr}_3$). These compounds could have a five-co-ordinated tin as suggested by Brune and Zeil¹⁶ and have the structure $(\text{SnX}_4 \cdot \text{Br})^+ \cdot \text{POBr}_2^+$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}$ or Br). Hexa-co-ordination is, however, the most favoured state for tin; Spandau *et al.*¹⁵, who have worked on tin(IV) chloride as a solvent, have shown the existence of $(\text{SnCl}_5)^+$ and $(\text{SnCl}_6)^{2-}$ ions only. Another representation of its structure may be based on the existence of the monobromo-oxophosphonium ion $(\text{POBr})^{2+}$ which has already been visualised in the present communication in the case of $\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 2\text{SO}_2$.

Antimony(V) chloride reacts with phosphoryl bromide to provide a pale yellow solid compound, antimony(V) chloride-phosphoryl bromide ($\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{POBr}_3$). It is very hygroscopic and has a conductance of $4.48 \times 10^{-4} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 150° (molten state), which is appreciable as compared to the conductance of the individual components and shows its slightly ionic nature. Antimony is known to acquire a six-co-ordination in most of its complexes¹⁷. On the basis of the proposed ionisation of the solvent, the nature of the complex may be represented as

Aluminium chloride and aluminium bromide, both, combine with phosphoryl bromide to afford solid compounds, $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$ and $\text{AlBr}_3 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$. These compounds are soluble in nitrobenzene (sp. conductance = $1.3264 \times 10^{-4} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1.9418 \times 10^{-4} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at concentrations of 0.0099 g. moles and 0.0107 g. moles per 1000 g. nitrobenzene). The sp. conductance of these compounds is quite high as compared to that of the individual components, indicating their ionic nature. Molecular weights of the two compounds in

14. Wyckoff, *Amer. J. Sci.*, 1928, 15, 287.

15. Rosenheim and Schutte, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1901, 26, 239.

16. Brune and Zeil, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1962, 32, 364.

17. Sidgwick, "Chemical Elements & their Compounds," Vol. I, 1950, p. 800.

nitrobenzene indicate their monomolecularity. Aluminium is known to have a tendency to acquire tetra- and hexa-co-ordination¹⁸ as $(\text{AlCl}_4)^-$ and $(\text{AlF}_6)^{3-}$. Therefore the structure of the two compounds may be represented as

(where X=Cl, Br).

The compounds $\text{AlX}_3 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$ could also be represented as $(\text{AlX}_3 \cdot \text{Br}_2)^{2-}$ and $2(\text{POBr}_2)^+$. This, however, shows a penta-co-ordination for aluminium, which seems to be improbable.

FIG. 5 Freezing point diagram.

Antimony(III) bromide dissolves in molten phosphoryl bromide in all proportions. Freezing point curves of mixtures is presented in Fig. 5 and indicates a simple eutectic at 40 mole% of antimony(III) bromide. To ascertain the possibility of existence of any compound formation, the specific conductance is plotted against molar ratio (Sb^{III} bromide/phosphoryl bromide) at 60° (Fig. 1). The sp. conductance of antimony(III) bromide is $2.44 \times 10^{-4} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 90°, but the sp. conduc-

18. Sidgwick, *ibid.*, p. 425.

tance of the mixtures is definitely higher. The conductance curve also shows a slight discontinuity at molar ratio of (Sb^{III} bromide/phosphoryl bromide) of 1 : 1, probably indicating the formation of a compound POBr₃.SbBr₃. In view of the conductance of the solutions and the tetra-co-ordination of antimony¹⁹, the nature of the solutions may be represented as:

The Lewis acids, sulphur trioxide, tin (IV) bromide, tin (IV) chloride, titanium (IV) chloride, antimony (V) chloride, aluminium chloride, aluminium bromide, and antimony (III) bromide, react with this solvent as a result of which the concentration of dibromo-oxo-phosphonium (POBr₂)⁺ ions is increased. According to equation (i) (POBr₂)⁺ is the cation specific to the solvent phosphoryl bromide; therefore all these Lewis acids will act as solvo-acids.

The crystal structures of SnCl₄.2POCl₃²⁰, TiCl₄.2POCl₃²¹, TiCl₄.POCl₃²², SbCl₅.POCl₃²³⁻²⁴, NbCl₅.POCl₃²⁴, TaCl₅.POCl₃²¹, and SbCl₅.PO(CH₃)₃²⁴⁻²⁵ have been interpreted as being due to oxygen co-ordination. The IR spectra of solid addition compounds between phosphoryl halides and metal halides indicate a shift in the P-O stretching frequency to a lower one with respect to pure phosphoryl halide. This has been interpreted by Sheldon and Tyree⁴ as suggesting that the bonding in the addition compound is through oxygen. IR spectra of POCl₃.BCl₃, Ph₃POCl.BCl₃, and Ph₃PO.BCl₃²⁶ and Raman spectra of POCl₃.AlCl₃ and POCl₃.GaCl₃ in liquid state²⁷ have also been interpreted as being due to oxygen co-ordination. These views are supported by the recent work of Wartenberg and Goubeau²⁸.

The structure of phosphoryl chloride-boron trichloride complex by IR spectra²⁸, however, supports the view that the ionic species (POCl₂)⁺ and (BCl₄)⁻ exist in the compound POCl₃.BCl₃. Raman spectra²⁹, conductance³⁰, and transport measurements³¹ of some of these compounds either in the liquid state or as solutes in the liquid phosphoryl chloride have also been offered as support for their ionic structures. It therefore seems quite probable that these addition compounds (general formula xMX_n.yPOX₃, where X=Cl or Br and M=metal) when dissolved in phosphoryl halides do provide ions of the type POX₂⁺ and MX_{n-1}⁻, or MX_{n+2}²⁻, whereas in solid state these may have different structures which have been indicated by X-ray study of crystals and IR study of the solids mentioned earlier.

19. Sidgwick, *ibid.*, p. 798.

20. Branden, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1963, 17, 759.

21. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1962, 16, 1808.

22. Branden *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1960, 14, 726.

23. Lindqvist and Branden, *Acta Cryst.*, 1959, 12, 642.

24. Branden *et al.*, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1963, 17, 353.

25. Branden *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1961, 15, 167.

26. Peach and Waddington, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 3460.

27. Gerding *et al.*, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1960, 16, 881.

28. Gerrad *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4255.

29. Gutmann and Himmel, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1955, 4, 157.

30. Greenwood and Wade, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1516.

31. Maschka *et al.*, *Monatsh.*, 1955, 86, 52.

Anhydrous lithium bromide furnishes a fine yellow crystalline solid solvate, lithium bromide-phosphoryl bromide ($\text{LiBr} \cdot \text{POBr}_3$). Its solutions in phosphoryl bromide and nitrobenzene are conducting. Sp. conductance of its solution (0.00357 g. moles/1000 g. phosphoryl bromide) is $3.578 \times 10^{-3} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 60° . Sp. conductance of its solution (0.0074 g. moles/1000 g. nitrobenzene) is $3.072 \times 10^{-3} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 20° . The sp. conductance values clearly indicate that the compound $\text{LiBr} \cdot \text{POBr}_3$ is ionic in nature. Since lithium bromide ionises as: $\text{LiBr} \rightarrow (\text{Li})^+ + (\text{Br})^-$, the probable mode of ionisation of $\text{LiBr} \cdot \text{POBr}_3$ may be represented as

The electron-acceptor behaviour of phosphoryl bromide with nitrogen bases, as in the case of lithium bromide, is indicated by the formation of compounds between the two. With the exception of pyridine, dimethylformamide, and quinoline, all other bases form solid compounds having the general formula $(\text{Base})_3 \cdot \text{POBr}_3$. Pyridine and dimethylformamide form compounds of the type $(\text{Base})_4 \cdot \text{POBr}_3$, whereas dimethylformamide and quinoline provide compounds of the general formula $(\text{Base})_n \cdot \text{POBr}_3$ as well. Quinoline forms a complex of composition $\text{POBr}_3 \cdot \text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}$, also. All these compounds are hygroscopic and insoluble in nonprotonic solvents. These are, however, soluble in water but are decomposed by it. These compounds are mostly high-melting and nonvolatile, indicating their nature as fairly ionic. Their ionic nature is further supported by a study of the conductance of pyridine, α -picoline, dimethylaniline, and quinoline solutions in phosphoryl bromide. A plot of sp. conductance vs. molar ratio of (base/phosphoryl bromide) is presented in Fig. 6.

FIG. 6. Specific conductance of bases in phosphoryl bromide at 60° .

Except for quinoline, conductance at higher concentrations could not be studied due to

limited solubility of these bases in phosphoryl bromide. Quinoline is miscible with phosphoryl bromide in all proportions; the plot of sp. conductance vs. concentration shows sharp breaks at molar ratios (quinoline/phosphoryl bromide) of 1:1, 2:1, and 3:1, indicating formation of the complexes $C_9H_7N \cdot POBr_3$, $(C_9H_7N)_2 \cdot POBr_3$ and $(C_9H_7N)_3 \cdot POBr_3$. On the basis of strong electron-donor properties of the bases and the ionisation of the solvent, as indicated by equation (i), the higher conductance of solutions of the bases in phosphoryl bromide in comparison to that of the components can be explained as

It is possible that more than one bromide ion may be replaced in the compounds containing higher proportion of the bases. The general structures may be represented as

It is rather difficult to visualise the structure of the compounds $POBr_3$, $4C_5H_5N$ and $POBr_3 \cdot 4D.M.F.$ (D.M.F. = dimethylformamide). However, on the basis of hexa-coordination of phosphorus³² as $(PF_6)^-$ in hexafluorophosphate or as $(PCl_6)^-$ in phosphorus pentachloride crystals, it could be represented as

The solvates of phosphoryl bromide in dimethylformamide, having much larger proportions of the latter, can be explained on the basis of the solvation of bromide ions in it.

While explaining the conductance of the Lewis acids in phosphoryl bromide, the structure of the compounds formed has been shown to be based on the formation or the liberation of the ions of the type $(POBr_2)^+$ and $(POBr)^{2+}$. These ions are the cations specific to the solvent phosphoryl bromide and therefore the Lewis acids may act as solvo-acids in this medium. In dilute solutions the formation of dibromo-oxophosphonium ions $(POBr_2)^+$ only can be visualised. Since at low concentrations the solutions are conducting, lithium bromide is expected to act as an ansolvo-base and the rest of the tertiary bases are expected to act as solvo-bases. If these conclusions are correct, it should be possible to study their mutual neutralisation. With this end in view, conductometric titrations were carried out. A change in the conductance of solutions of bases with the addition of acidic solutions has been studied and relative conductance has been plotted against molar ratio (Sn^{IV} bromide/base) in Fig. 7. In the case of α -picoline and dimethylaniline, the addition of tin(IV) bromide results in a slight decrease in conductance till the molar ratio (Sn^{IV} bromide/base) of 0.5:1 is reached. This can be explained on the basis of the following reaction:

(where B = base).

32. Sidgwick, "Chemical Elements & their Compounds," Vol. I, 1950, p. 766.

FIG. 7. Conductometric titrations of tin (iv) bromide with bases in phosphoryl bromide at 60°.

Further addition of tin (iv) bromide results in a rapid increase in conductance till the molar ratio (Sn^{IV} bromide/base) of 1:1 is reached. Further additions of tin (iv) bromide results in a slight decrease in the conductance due possibly to the dilution effect. The 1:1 neutralisation corresponds to the formation of an acid salt as in the case of a dibasic acid. The complex may be represented as

Since this has a high concentration of $(\text{POBr}_2)^+$ ions, it has a much higher conductance than that of the normal salt formed at 0.5 : 1 molar ratio of acid and base. The conductometric titration curves of lithium bromide and quinoline also show breaks representing formation of 1 : 2 compounds and in the case of lithium bromide, a 1 : 1 compound also. These titrations thus definitely support the existence of the indicated ionic species in phosphoryl bromide, which may be summarised as:

EXPERIMENTAL

Phosphoryl bromide was prepared and purified as described by Greenwood and Worrall⁵. Various solvents, Lewis acids, and bases used were purified by methods already in use.

Preparation of Complexes

1. $\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 2\text{SO}_3$.—Sulphur trioxide (4 g.) was distilled directly into solid phosphoryl bromide (7 g.) when a dark red viscous liquid was produced in an exothermic reaction. Excess of sulphur trioxide was removed by submitting the liquid to a high vacuum and was further purified by distilling at $86^\circ/75\text{Cmm}$. (Found: Br, 53.0; S, 14.1; P, 6.8. Calc. for $\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 2\text{SO}_3$: Br, 53.2; S, 14.3; P, 6.9%). Density = 2.439 g.ml^{-1} at 25° ; viscosity = 35.55 c.p. at 25° .

2. $\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$.—Tin(IV) bromide (3 g.) was added to molten phosphoryl bromide (4 g.) when a light yellow liquid was produced. The compound was purified by distilling at $70^\circ/6 \text{ mm}$ (decomposes at 125°). (Found: Br, 78.7; P, 5.9; Sn, 11.4. Calc. for $\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$: Br, 79.0; P, 6.1, Sn, 11.6%). Density = 3.07 g.ml^{-1} at 25° ; viscosity = 4.33 c.p. at 25° .

Solid complexes of tin(IV) chloride, titanium(IV) chloride, antimony(V) chloride with phosphoryl bromide were prepared by mixing the two constituents in CCl_4 medium.

3. $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$.—It is a white needle-shaped crystalline compound, very hygroscopic, and is decomposed by water. It is soluble in chloroform, carbon disulphide, and fairly soluble in benzene; m.p. 90° . (Found: Br, 57.4; P, 7.3; Sn, 14.0. Calc. for $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$: Br, 57.5; P, 7.2; Sn, 14.1%).

4. $\text{TiCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$.—It is a very hygroscopic orange-red solid and is decomposed by water. It is soluble in dry ether, benzene, carbon disulphide, and nitrobenzene and only slightly soluble in chloroform; m.p. 160° . [Found: Br, 62.5; Ti, 6.2; P, 7.9; M. W. (nitrobenzene), 766. Calc. for $\text{TiCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$: Br, 62.8; Ti, 6.3; P, 8.0%; M. W., 764].

5. $\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{POBr}_3$.—It is a pale yellow compound, extremely hygroscopic and is easily decomposed by water. It is soluble in chloroform and carbon disulphide but only slightly soluble in benzene. Specific conductance at $150^\circ = 4.484 \times 10^{-4} \text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$. (Found: P, 5.3; Sb, 21.2; Br, 40.5; Cl, 30.1. Calc. for $\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{POBr}_3$: P, 5.3; Sb, 21.1; Br, 40.9; Cl, 30.3%).

Solid complexes of AlCl_3 , AlBr_3 , and LiBr were prepared by refluxing these with large excess of phosphoryl bromide. The homogeneous solutions, thus obtained, were cooled and excess of phosphoryl bromide was removed by repeated washing with CCl_4 .

6. $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$.—It does not melt up to 250° . It is cream-coloured, hygroscopic, and is decomposed by water. It is slightly soluble in CS_2 and CHCl_3 and soluble in nitrobenzene. It is insoluble in benzene and nitromethane. [Found: Al, 3.7; P, 8.7; Br, 67.5;

Cl, 15.0; M.W. (nitrobenzene), 730. Calc. for $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$: Al, 3.8; P, 8.8; Br, 67.8; Cl, 15.05%; M.W., 708].

Sp. conductance of the solution (0.0099 g. moles/1000 g.) in nitrobenzene = $1.3264 \times 10^{-4} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

7. $\text{AlBr}_3 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$.—It is a white crystalline, hygroscopic compound, decomposed by water. It is slightly soluble in chloroform and benzene and soluble in nitrobenzene; m.p. 215°. [Found: Al, 3.2; P, 7.4; Br, 85; M.W. (nitrobenzene), 856. Calc. for $\text{AlBr}_3 \cdot 2\text{POBr}_3$: Al, 3.2; P, 7.4; Br, 85.6%; M.W., 841]. The above compound can also be prepared by mixing the two constituents in CS_2 medium. Sp. conductance of solution (0.0107 g. moles/1000 g.) in nitrobenzene = $1.9418 \times 10^{-4} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

8. $\text{LiBr} \cdot \text{POBr}_3$.—It is light yellow, hygroscopic, and is decomposed by water. It is slightly soluble in CCl_4 , nitrobenzene, phosphoryl bromide, and freely soluble in chloroform. It does not melt up to 220°. (Found: Br, 86.9; Li, 1.8; P, 8.2. Calc. for $\text{LiBr} \cdot \text{POBr}_3$: Br, 87.2; Li, 1.9; P, 8.4%). Sp. conductance of solution (0.0074 g. moles/1000 g.) in nitrobenzene = $3.072 \times 10^{-5} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Specific conductance of solution (0.0387 g. moles/1000 g.) in phosphoryl bromide = $3.518 \times 10^{-5} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Compounds with Organic Bases

The compounds of bases with phosphoryl bromide (*vide infra* and Table I) were prepared under similar conditions in dry CCl_4 . These were filtered and washed with CCl_4 under perfectly dry conditions. Excess of the solvent was removed in vacuum. Formation of complexes with bases was an exothermic process and controlled by cooling in an ice bath. All these compounds are hygroscopic and are decomposed by water. These are insoluble in common nonprotic organic solvents.

9. $\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 2\text{D.M.F.}$.—Dimethylformamide (3 g.) was added dropwise to phosphoryl bromide (6 g.) with continuous shaking when a fine cream-coloured crystalline solid separated. It is slightly soluble in chloroform. (Found: Br, 55.2; P, 7.1; N, 6.3. Calc. for $\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 2\text{D.M.F.}$: Br, 55.4; P, 7.15; N, 6.46%).

10. $\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 4\text{D.M.F.}$.—Phosphoryl bromide (5 g.) was added dropwise to dimethylformamide (6 g.) when a white crystalline compound separated. (Found: Br, 41.2; P, 5.2; N, 9.5. Calc. for $\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 4\text{D.M.F.}$: Br, 41.4; P, 5.35; N, 9.67%). This compound on keeping in vacuum (6 mm) for 3 hr. at 100° furnished $\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 2\text{D.M.F.}$

11. $\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 5\text{D.M.F.}$.—Phosphoryl bromide (5 g.) was added dropwise to dimethylformamide (8 g.) when a white solid separated. The resulting mixture was refluxed over a water bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. when the white solid product changed to a yellow solid. (Found: Br, 36.4; P, 4.7; N, 10.6. Calc. for $\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 5\text{D.M.F.}$: Br, 36.8; P, 4.75; N, 10.7%). This compound was subjected to a vacuum (6 mm) for 2 hr. at 100° when a light yellow residue was obtained. (Found: Br, 47.3; P, 6.0; N, 8.3. Calc. for $\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 3\text{D.M.F.}$: Br, 47.4; P, 6.1; N, 8.3%).

The above compound was further subjected to a vacuum (6 mm. Hg) at 150° when a cream-coloured solid ($\text{POBr}_3 \cdot 2\text{D.M.F.}$) sublimed on the cooler parts.

TABLE I
Phosphoryl bromide complexes with bases.

Compound formed.	POBr ₃ added.	Base added.	% Bromine.		% Phosphorus.		% Nitrogen.		M.P.	Colour.	Solubility.
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.			
POBr ₃ ·4C ₂ H ₅ N	5.0 g.	6.0 g.	39.6	39.8	5.0	5.1	0.1	0.2	163°	White	Soluble in molten phosphoryl bromide; insoluble in solvents.*
POBr ₃ ·3C ₂ H ₅ N(α)	6.0	6.0	42.2	42.4	5.3	5.5	7.4	7.4	..	Dark red	Do.
POBr ₃ ·8C ₂ H ₅ N(γ)	6.0	6.0	42.3	42.4	5.3	5.5	7.3	7.4	86°(d)	Orange-red	Slightly soluble in CHCl ₃ & molten phosphoryl bromide; insoluble in solvents*.
POBr ₃ ·9C ₂ H ₅ N(δ)	3.0	4.0	35.3	35.5	4.5	4.6	6.2	6.2	184°	Pale yellow	Soluble in EtOH, CHCl ₃ , slightly soluble in molten phosphoryl bromide; insoluble in solvents*.
POBr ₃ ·3(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ NC ₂ H ₅	4.6	7.5	36.7	36.0	4.6	4.7	6.4	6.5	..	Light yellow	Soluble in molten phosphoryl bromide; insoluble in solvents.*
POBr ₃ ·3(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ NC ₂ H ₅	3.0	4.6	32.4	32.5	4.1	4.2	5.7	5.7	155°	Pale yellow	Soluble in CHCl ₃ , EtOH, molten phosphoryl bromide; insoluble in solvents*.

*Solvents: Benzene, CCl₄, petroleum, CS₂, cyclohexane, nitrobenzene, and acetone.

Measurements of Conductance.—The resistance of the solutions was measured as already described by Paul *et al*³³. The cell was kept in a bath maintained at constant temperature. The conductometric titrations were carried out by adding the titrant by weight and not by volume as it was solid at the room temperature.

Thermal analysis was carried out by cooling curve method and molecular weights were determined by depression in freezing point.

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